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State-Public Management of Vocational and Pedagogical Education in the Region

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Abstract

The relevance of the study is due to the positioning of teacher education as a state-public system. The purpose of the article is to develop a mechanism of state-public management of vocational and pedagogical education in the region. The methodological basis of the study was a set of principles of systematization, concretization, participativeness, allowing to establish relationships between the subjects of management. The main results of the research consist in substantiating the social partnership of organizers of pedagogical education; the creation of public institutions for the management of the quality of teacher education; integration of the subjects of management. The study involved 38 heads of educational organizations, 150 teachers, 430 students, who identified the criteria for assessing state-public management (rational, social). The significance of the results obtained is that social partnership ensures the organization of an educational consortium. The creation of public institutions for the management of the quality of education provides a public discussion of the evaluation criteria and transparency of the control procedure. The integration of the subjects of management provides networking for various logical reasons. The revealed criteria contribute to the conjugation of professional and educational standards (rational), the improvement of the system of continuous pedagogical education on the basis of consolidation and variable interaction of its subjects (social). In the course of the experiment, state-public structures of education management were created.

Keywords: state-public administration, teacher education, continuing teacher education.

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Introduction

The relevance of the study is due to the development of civil society and the positioning of teacher education as an open, state-public system (Freedman, Willigan, Glading, & Rainville, 2018). At the present stage, pedagogical education, as a sphere of social policy, ceases to interest only the pedagogical community. Requirements for the activities of educational organizations providing teacher training are increasing (Gutman et al., 2015). They entail significant changes in governance processes at the institutional level and the nature of relations between the state, society, the pedagogical community (Kozhanova et al., 2016). It is established that the state, forming a civil society, seeks to maintain a balance between the groups that determine its interests. This determines the movement of pedagogical education towards supporting the public initiative in the field of educational services (Lavrentiev, Krylov, Komelina, & Arefieva, 2015). Pedagogical education becomes not only an open state-public system, but also a real means of leveling the scientific, educational and economic potentials of the regions (Valeeva & Salyakhova, 2015). The creation of a mechanism of state-public management of pedagogical education ensures the development of regional vocational education systems that are adequate to the specifics of the region and are focused on the demand of the regional labor market (Krylov, Lavrentiev, Komelina, Arefieva, & Shvetsov, 2016).

Management is a goal-oriented process of planning, organizing, motivating and controlling, ensuring the joint activities of the organization's employees.

Management of pedagogical education is a goal-oriented process of interaction between state authorities, education authorities, subjects of management of educational organizations, civil society institutions, aimed at ensuring the optimal functioning and development of pedagogical education in the region with the aim of obtaining qualitatively new results.

The essence of state-public management of pedagogical education is the productive interaction of educational organizations engaged in the training of teachers, education authorities, state, regional and municipal authorities, public organizations, aimed at (1) meeting the needs of the region in training teachers, (2) ensuring continuity of teacher education.

The subjects of state-public management of pedagogical education in the region are:

- authorities and education authorities, whose powers include the creation of educational standards and control over their implementation; accreditation of vocational education institutions; creating conditions for the development of continuing education;
- regional authorities and education authorities, whose tasks are to perform executive and administrative functions in the field of education and science in the region; providing training of highly qualified teaching staff;
- municipal education authorities, whose competencies include the formation of a social order for pedagogical education in the interests of the municipal district;
- accredited organizations providing professional educational services in the field of teacher education;
- corporate structures (teacher training institutes, training centers) responsible for the improvement of professional training of teachers;
- private individuals licensed to specific types of educational activities;
- consumers of educational services in the field of pedagogical education.

State-public management of pedagogical education provides for (1) the division of powers between management levels (federal, regional, municipal, local), (2) development of interconnections between management entities along the vertical (co-management and self-government) and horizontal (cooperation,

mutual assistance, organization of commissions, councils, etc.), (3) definition of clear functional competences of each subject of management.

It has been established that in the process of state-public management of pedagogical education, an interrelation is established between the activities of subjects of state and public administration, capable of initiating, discussing, making and implementing managerial decisions. In this case, the role of initiators of interaction is assumed by professionals working in the system of management of pedagogical education. As the role of civil society institutions in the management of pedagogical education increases, initiators of interaction create more and more conditions for joint activities with them.

The purpose of the article is to develop a mechanism of state-public management of pedagogical education in the region.

Methodological grounds

Management principles generalize existing knowledge, synthesizing them into a coherent whole; they are the basis for the construction of a scientific theory, ensuring its validity and further development; determine the basic requirements for content and methods of management. The methodological basis of the study was a set of principles of systematization, concretization, participativeness, allowing to establish the relationship between the motivation of the participation of civil society institutions in the management of vocational and pedagogical education in the region; state policy on the creation of new social relations in the system of continuous pedagogical education; development of forms of joint activity of subjects of management of pedagogical education in the region.

The principle of consistency ensures the development of the following properties of teacher education:

1) non-additive (non-reducibility of system properties to the sum of properties of its components, which is manifested in the development of co-management, self-government, cooperation, mutual assistance, and the organization of councils and funds, public relations, open competitions for pedagogical projects, public hearings)

2) the vertical integrity of teacher education in the region, manifested in the proportionality of the rights, duties, responsibilities of subjects and objects of state-public administration;

3) horizontal isolation of pedagogical education in the region, characterized by the expansion of the independence of the subjects of state-public administration, the development of public initiative in the provision of educational services for the preparation and improvement of teaching staff;

4) openness, manifested in the participation of civil society institutions in the management of pedagogical education, through the organization of trustees, alumni councils, public foundations, foresight projects, fundraising campaigns, public hearings, auditing the quality of pedagogical education by independent experts.

The principle of specification focuses on the choice of methods of state-public management of pedagogical education, taking into account the specific situation. Methods of state-public administration can be divided into several groups: 1) organizational and administrative, regulated by the current normative acts; 2) economic, providing for variable material incentives (valuable gifts, awards) and the organization of fundraising campaigns; 3) sociological (questioning, testing, PR actions, open competitions for educational projects, public hearings); 4) the foresight method for determining the prospects for the development of teacher education in the region.

The principle of participativeness is aimed at the development of social partnership of educational organizations with students and their parents, civil society institutions, employers, government and municipal authorities in order to form and implement educational policy in the region and make teacher education open to

society and accountable to it.

In the process of research, the following methods were used: theoretical (analysis, synthesis, synthesis, specification, systematization); sociological (observation, interviews, questioning, focus group method); pedagogical experiment.

The experimental base of the study was Kazan (Volga region) Federal University in Kazan (Russia). The pilot work involved 38 heads of educational organizations, 60 specialists of education authorities, 41 members of the board of trustees of Kazan (Volga region) Federal University and institutes, 6 heads of charitable foundations, 150 teachers, 430 students and 350 parents, 289 members of the public, 15 leaders of public organizations. Probabilistic samples were compiled.

The sample of heads of educational organizations includes directors of institutes, deputy directors, heads of departments, directors of scientific centers, members of the academic council of Kazan Federal University and institutes (average age 49 years).

The sample of specialists of education authorities includes 46 employees of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Tatarstan (average age 49 years), 14 employees of the Education Administration of the city of Kazan (average age 53 years).

The sample of participants in the Board of Trustees of Kazan (Volga region) Federal University and institutes included 41 people (average age 55 years). The sample of managers of charitable foundations included 4 employees of the National Union of Philanthropists of Kazan (average age 44 years) and 2 employees of the Joy of Childhood Foundation (average age 43 years).

The sample of teachers includes professors (average age 49 years) and associate professors (average age 37 years), who conduct training sessions with students enrolled in the direction of "Pedagogical education" and receive the qualification "bachelor".

The sample of students included students of 3-4 courses, enrolled in the direction of training "Pedagogical education" and get the qualification "bachelor".

The sample of parents included parents of students of 3-4 courses, enrolled in the direction of training "Pedagogical education" and receiving the qualification "bachelor" (the average age of parents 51 years).

The sample of members of the public included members of the university graduates association (average age 43 years), associations of young scientists (average age 29 years), university league women (average age 47 years).

The sample of leaders of public organizations includes leaders of the Council of Elders of the University (average age 61 years), League of Students (average age 22 years).

Nobody refused to participate in the experimental work. Participants in the experimental work identified the criteria for assessing the state-public management of vocational-pedagogical education in the region (rational, social).

The study was conducted in three stages. At the first stage, the goal, methodological basis and methods of research were determined, a mechanism of state-public management of pedagogical education was developed, and a plan of experimental work was drawn up.

At the second stage, experimental work was carried out to verify the effectiveness of the mechanism of state-public management of pedagogical education. Experimental work had three stages (stating, forming, control). At the ascertaining stage, with the help of questioning, the attitude of the participants in the experimental work to state-public management of pedagogical education was determined, and the criteria for its evaluation (rational, social) were determined. Questionnaires included

open and closed questions. The survey results were discussed in 11 focus groups, each of which included 9 people (the head of an educational organization, a specialist in an education management body, a member of the board of trustees, a head of a charitable foundation, a teacher, students and their parents, a public representative, a leader of public organizations). The participants were personally invited to the focus groups who were not familiar with each other. At the formative stage, state-public structures for the management of pedagogical education (trusteeship and coordination council, volunteer organizations, public associations) were created, which organized and conducted public relations campaigns, fundraising campaigns, open competitions for innovative projects, and public hearings. At the control stage, the stages of state-public management of professional and pedagogical education in the region were identified and substantiated: analytical-prognostic, program-targeted, design-activity, correctional-regulating, estimated-informational.

At the third stage of the study, the prospects for studying the problem of state-public management of vocational-pedagogical education in the region are defined.

Results

The mechanism of state-public management of vocational-pedagogical education includes social partnership of educational institutions, government officials and the local community; the creation of public institutions for the quality management of vocational and pedagogical education; integration of subjects of state-public management of pedagogical education.

Social partnership ensures the intensive development of its constituent entities through the organization of quasi-integration structures aimed at developing sustainable long-term relationships and delegating control over the management of joint activities in the absence of a legally executed transfer of rights and obligations (educational consortium).

The creation of public institutions for the management of the quality of pedagogical education provides a public discussion of the evaluation criteria and transparency of the control procedure.

Integration of subjects of state-public management of pedagogical education provides networking for various logical grounds and coordination of functions, coordination of actions, transfer of information based on a system of explicit and implicit contracts.

Experimental work on testing the effectiveness of the mechanism of state-public management of vocational-pedagogical education in the region had three stages (ascertaining, formative, control).

At the ascertaining stage, using the questionnaire, the attitude of the participants in the experimental work to the state-public management of pedagogical education was clarified (Table 1).

Table 1

The results of the survey of the participants of the experimental work on the question "Mark the necessary components of the mechanism state-public management of pedagogical education", carried out in October 2018 (%)

participants of experimental work	components of the mechanism of state-public management of pedagogical education		
	social partnership	the creation of	integration

	of educational institutions, government representatives and the local community	public institutions for the management of quality pedagogical education	of subjects of public management
heads of educational organization	84	36	96
education authorities	91	79	92
members of the board of trustees	83	46	93
charity fund managers	97	89	95
the teachers	76	24	89
the students	84	48	91
parents of students	89	89	93
member of the public	93	92	96
community leaders	98	96	94

From table 1 it can be seen that the attitude of the participants in the experimental work to the components of the mechanism of state-public management of pedagogical education is not unambiguous, different. Analysis of the answers to open questions about the properties of the components of the mechanism of state-public administration led to the following conclusions:

1) the majority of the participants in the experimental work include the interest of each partner in finding the optimal forms and methods of functioning and development of teacher education (95%) as properties of social partnership; good faith (89%); equal cooperation (92%); the emergence of goals and non-additive interests of each partner (97%);

2) to the properties of public institutions, the majority of participants in the experimental work include informing the public about the activities of educational organizations (91%); organization of special seminars on the procedure for assessing the quality of pedagogical education by independent expert commissions (97%); public discussion of criteria for assessing the quality of teacher education in the region (99%); ensuring the transparency of the procedure for monitoring the quality of teacher education (82%);

3) the majority of the participants in the experimental work relate network interaction on the basis of various logical grounds to the properties of integration of subjects of state-public administration: concentration of resources (93%); coordination of functions (97%); coordination of actions (98%); transfer information (91%).

According to the results of the survey, the focus group participants defined the criteria for assessing the state-public management of pedagogical education in the region (rational, social).

At the formative stage, target groups were created from the participants in the experimental work, which developed programs for implementing the mechanism of state-public education management in the region, including activities and timelines.

State-public structures for the management of pedagogical education (volunteer organizations, public associations, coordination council) were created, which organized and conducted PR campaigns, fundraising campaigns, open competitions for educational projects, and public hearings.

The volunteer organizations included students and their parents, teachers, members of the public. In October 2018, volunteers organized the “Marathon of Good Deeds”. In just the first 7 days of October, volunteers organized and held in orphanages more than 100 actions and events, including creative workshops, numerous charity events, fairs, flash mobs, theatrical performances, game programs of a trip to orphanages.

During one of the master classes, volunteers offered children a variety of materials for handicrafts: leaves, cereals, plasticine, colored paper and much more. The guys with great pleasure to put their ideas into practice. The theme was autumn motives, and the children used all the proposed tools and materials, which served as both an entertaining game and an exciting learning experience. Developing fine motor skills, everyone managed to realize his or her idea on cardboard, which became a kind of canvas for young artists.

On October 7, the school of the “Volunteer” asset was organized, in which 80 students took part. During the day, school participants learned how to organize pedagogical projects, and discussed the topic “Assistance to orphans: material or psychological.”

Since 2007, the Student Volunteer Center has been operating, called to assist in the formation of an active citizenship among young people, their involvement in the process of voluntary socially significant and socially useful activities, instilling a sense of respect for other people. The activity of the center is carried out through multidirectional project work, the result of which are events of various levels. For example: targeted assistance to socially unprotected categories of citizens (pensioners, disabled people, veterans of the Great Patriotic War and home front workers, orphans); actions aimed at protecting the environment, promoting a healthy lifestyle; donor shares; assistance to homeless shelters; improvement of burial places of prominent university scientists.

In 2010, the Coordination Council was established to consolidate and integrate the subjects of vocational education management, develop student government and enhance the role of students in the modernization of teacher education. In 2018, the Coordination Council organized an open competition of projects for the modernization of practice-oriented teacher training among university teachers. The participants of the competition, within the framework of a specific discipline that students study, developed a complex of educational and educational activities that ensure the readiness of the future teacher to learn, educate and develop students, taking into account their age, psychophysical and individual characteristics. Project evaluation criteria: 1) novelty; 2) the appropriateness of the application; 3) correctness in the use of copyright materials. Participation in the competition was individual.

The Coordination Council organized a public hearing of the project on the practice-oriented training of future teachers based on the network interaction of higher education institutions and basic general education. The subject of network interaction are: forms, methods, means of implementing educational tasks; upgrading the skills of school teachers and university professors; audit of educational activities of the university and the school.

At the control stage, focus groups evaluated the state-public management of vocational-pedagogical education in the region (rational, social) (Table 2).

Table 2

The results of the assessment of state-public management of pedagogical education by focus groups on a five-point system at the ascertaining and control stages of experimental work (average score)

Criteria and indicators	Stages of experimental work
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	ing	ascertain	control
1. Rational			
1.1. Organization of social partnership of educational institutions, government officials and the local community		4	5
1.2. Establishment of public institutions for the quality management of teacher education		3	5
2. Social			
2.1. Integration of subjects of state and public administration		3	5
2.2. Dialogue of educational institutions with students and their parents, representatives of civil institutions, employers		3	5

From Table 2 it can be seen that at the control stage of experimental work, the focus groups rated the state-public management of pedagogical education in the region by 5 points. This allows you to say that the mechanism of state-public administration is effective. The stages of state-public management of pedagogical education are revealed: 1) analytical and prognostic, based on the analysis of the situation, forecast of the development of pedagogical education; 2) program-target, in the course of which the goal, tasks are defined and a set of measures is developed for their achievement; 3) project-activity, which implements a set of measures and creates conditions for the development of teacher education; 4) correctional and regulatory, providing control and correction of the management process, program activities; 5) estimated and informational, providing an objective assessment of the prospects for the development of pedagogical education and setting the following tasks.

Discussions

The problem of state-public management of pedagogical education is attracting increasing attention of scientists (Gutman et al., 2015). This makes it possible to single out general and national trends in state-public management of pedagogical education. General trends include the organization of numerous international competitions for teachers (The Global Teacher Prize, 2018); presentation and popularization of the pedagogical experience of subject teachers (DeSantis, Boyd, Marks, Putsch, & Shepler, 2017; Morowski & McCormick, 2017); creating public associations, conducting PR actions, fundraising campaigns (Freedman et al., 2018; Haverback, 2017; Valeeva & Khakimova, 2015). If general trends reflect the strategy of improving state-public management of pedagogical education, national trends reflect the tactics of its implementation. The Russian tendencies of state-public management of pedagogical education include the creation of volunteer organizations, the holding of competitions for educational projects and public hearings (Kozhanova et al., 2016; Krylov et al., 2016; Lavrentiev et al., 2015; Valeeva & Salyakhova, 2015). The study of general and national trends is of great importance, since the strategies and tactics used can be interesting and useful, help to update the mechanism of state-public management of pedagogical education and improve its quality.

Conclusion

The relevance of the study is due to the development of civil society and the positioning of teacher

education as an open, state-public system. The methodological basis of the study was a set of principles of systematization, concretization, participativeness, allowing to establish the relationship between the motivation of the participation of civil society institutions in the management of teacher education; state policy on the creation of new social relations in the system of continuous pedagogical education; development of forms of joint activity of subjects of management of pedagogical education in the region.

The main results of the research consist in the development of a mechanism for state-public management of pedagogical education, including social partnership of educational institutions, government representatives and the local community; the creation of public institutions for the management of the quality of pedagogical education; integration of subjects of state-public management of pedagogical education. The significance of the results obtained lies in the fact that the social partnership of educational institutions, government officials and the local community ensures the intensive development of its constituent entities through the organization of quasi-integration structures aimed at developing sustainable long-term relationships and delegating control over the management of joint activities in the absence of legal transfer of rights and responsibilities (educational consortium). The creation of public institutions for the management of the quality of pedagogical education provides a public discussion of the evaluation criteria and transparency of the control procedure. Integration of subjects of state-public management of pedagogical education provides networking for various logical grounds and coordination of functions, coordination of actions, transfer of information based on a system of explicit and implicit contracts. The revealed criteria contribute to the conjugation of professional and educational standards (rational), the improvement of the system of continuous pedagogical education on the basis of consolidation and variable interaction of its subjects (social).

In the course of the experiment, state-public structures for the management of pedagogical education (trusteeship and coordination council, volunteer organizations, public associations) were created, which organized and conducted public relations campaigns, fundraising campaigns, open competitions for innovative projects, and public hearings. Analysis of the activities of state-public structures allowed to identify and justify the stages of state-public management of pedagogical education in the region: analytical and prognostic, program-targeted, design-activity, correctional-regulating, estimated-informational.

The article materials may be useful for teachers of institutions of professional pedagogical education; employees of centers of advanced training and retraining of scientific and pedagogical staff of universities and colleges of pedagogical profile.

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